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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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DR. ROVILYN K. DAGONDON

Associate Professor V

North Eastern Mindanao State University

rkdagondon@nemsu.edu.ph

“QUALITY OF WORK LIFE”

In this modern world, one of the main issues in academic organizations is the quality of work life of the faculty (Hamidi, 2012). It depends on their personal lives and their work through their level of contentment, enthusiasm, cooperation, and commitment in all organizational effectiveness and achieve organizational success (Chand, 2012). Moreover, to attract and retain faculty, it is essential for a university to have a high impact quality of work life of the faculty to effectively improve their productivity and performance for the attainment of their personal and organizational goals and objectives..

The periodic evaluation of quality of work life can implicitly provide the organization’s information towards the welfare of their faculty. Identifying employees’ potentials through their quality of work life can ensure that they will provide and commitment and participation in the organization. Additionally, continuous improvement of quality of work life will eventually lead to excellence and achieve organizational success. Moreover, quality of work life is an essential tool in today’s world wherein people are more volatile and competitive in the workplace.

